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The Ground Beneath Us: A Study on Earthquake Awareness and Emergency Preparedness among Residents of Koronadal City, Philippines

Jayson Diaz

College of Criminology, Green Valley College Foundation Inc., City of Koronadal, South Cotabato, Philippines

e-mail: jdiaz@gvcfi.edu.ph

* Corresponding Author: research@gvcfi.edu.ph

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to assess the level of earthquake awareness and emergency preparedness among adult residents in Koronadal City, a seismically active area along the Cotabato Fault System. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, it explores the relationship between residents' demographic profiles and their levels of awareness and preparedness. A validated structured questionnaire was used, measuring awareness and preparedness through a 5-point Likert scale across indicators such as earthquake causes, safety measures, local seismic history, evacuation plans, and emergency supplies. Stratified random sampling selected 421 respondents proportionally across the city's 27 barangays for geographic and demographic representation. Descriptive statistics summarized the demographic profile and assessed awareness and preparedness levels, while the Chi-Square Test of Independence at a 0.05 significance level tested associations between categorical variables. Findings revealed moderate to high awareness but varying preparedness across demographic groups. Demographic factors such as age, sex, and education influenced outcomes, highlighting the need for targeted disaster education.

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INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Earthquakes are among the most devastating natural hazards globally, capable of causing massive loss of life, destruction of infrastructure, and long-term economic disruption (CRED & UNDRR, 2022). Areas located along tectonic plate boundaries, particularly within the Pacific Ring of Fire, experience frequent seismic activity, underscoring the necessity of robust public awareness and preparedness strategies (USGS, 2023). Despite technological advances in seismic monitoring and early warning systems, communities, especially in developing countries, continue to suffer disproportionately due to low awareness and insufficient preparedness measures. (UNDRR, 2022; Wisner et al., 2012).

The Philippines, situated along the Pacific Ring of Fire, is highly vulnerable to seismic events due to multiple active fault lines, including the Philippine Fault Zone and Cotabato Fault System (PHIVOLCS, 2023). Major earthquakes in recent decades have led to significant casualties and infrastructure damage, emphasizing the urgent need for localized disaster risk reduction (DRR) initiatives (Lagmay et al., 2017). While national programs, such as the Nationwide Simultaneous Earthquake Drill (NSED), aim to improve public readiness, disparities persist across regions, particularly in data availability and public engagement in earthquake preparedness (NDRRMC, 2020; Delos Reyes et al., 2021).

Koronadal City in South Cotabato, Mindanao, lies near the Cotabato Fault System, making it moderately prone to seismic hazards. However, limited empirical research has focused on earthquake awareness and emergency preparedness in this urban center. Most existing studies concentrate on Metro Manila and other high-risk areas in Luzon and the Visayas (Garcia & Santos, 2019; Morales, 2022), leaving Mindanao, especially cities like Koronadal underrepresented in disaster preparedness research.

To bridge this gap, this study assesses the levels of earthquake awareness and emergency preparedness among residents of Koronadal City. It aims to profile residents demographically by age, sex, education, and location factors known to influence risk perception and behavioral response to disasters (Paton & Johnston, 2017; Lindell & Perry, 2012). The study further evaluates residents' knowledge of earthquake causes, local seismic history, and appropriate safety protocols. It also investigates preparedness behaviors, including familiarity with evacuation plans and possession of emergency supplies elements critical for reducing disaster-related losses (Tierney, 2019).

Findings from this research are intended to support local government units and disaster risk reduction agencies in crafting evidence-based, community-specific interventions that enhance earthquake resilience and public safety in Koronadal City.

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Literature Review

Demographic Factors and Earthquake Preparedness

Demographic characteristics such as age, sex, education level, and place of residence play a crucial role in shaping earthquake awareness and preparedness. Bourque (2015) found that demographic variables significantly influence how residents in California receive earthquake information and prepare for seismic events. Similarly, De Almeida et al. (2019) emphasized that the clinical and demographic profile of earthquake victims in Nepal affects their vulnerability and response capabilities. Paul and Bhuiyan (2010) highlighted that in Dhaka City, Bangladesh, urban residents' perceived seismic risk and preparedness levels vary by socioeconomic status and education, showing the importance of demographic context in disaster readiness. Moreover, Atando and Sugawara (2023) compared earthquake preparedness between low- and high-income populations in Japan and the Philippines, illustrating how income level as a demographic factor influences readiness. These findings suggest that demographic profiling is vital for targeted earthquake awareness and preparedness interventions.

Earthquake Awareness: Causes, Risks, and Local Seismic History

Understanding earthquake causes, associated risks, and local seismic history is fundamental for effective public awareness. Hutchings and Mooney (2024) provided a detailed seismotectonic overview of the Philippine subduction system, underscoring the geological risks faced by residents. Ferrario et al. (2024) studied the environmental impacts of recent Philippine earthquakes, highlighting the importance of local seismic history in community awareness. Penarubia et al. (2020) developed probabilistic seismic hazard models specific to the Philippines, which serve as critical educational tools for hazard communication. In addition, Perez et al. (2023) examined the impacts of the 2022 Northwestern Luzon earthquake, showing how localized earthquake events can enhance public consciousness of seismic threats. Together, these studies emphasize the need for region-specific awareness of earthquake causality and risks.

Earthquake Preparedness: Safety Measures, Evacuation, and Emergency Supplies

Preparedness measures such as knowledge of safety protocols, evacuation plans, and availability of emergency supplies directly influence outcomes during earthquakes. Rostami-Moez et al. (2020) identified predictors of household preparedness using the health belief model, finding that awareness and perceived risk motivate better preparation. Mancio et al. (2024) assessed the readiness of police stations in Metro Manila, highlighting institutional preparedness as a key component. Grozdanić et al. (2024) performed a cross-cultural analysis of sustainable earthquake preparedness, reinforcing that cultural context affects how communities plan and respond. Spittal et al. (2008) distinguished between different types of preparedness behaviors, stressing that both knowledge and practical action are needed. These studies collectively underline that preparedness is multi-dimensional, involving knowledge, planning, and resource availability.

Technological Advances and Earthquake Source Detection

Recent advances in machine learning and geoscience technology have improved earthquake source detection and prediction, which indirectly impact public awareness and preparedness strategies. Bharadwaj et al. (2023) explored using symmetric autoencoders for learning earthquake sources, while Gomez and Kadri (2021) applied machine learning algorithms to

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acoustic signals for source characterization. Lin et al. (2023) proposed a hybrid deep learning model for rapid earthquake parameter estimation. These technological advancements enhance seismic hazard assessment, offering more accurate and timely data that can improve community preparedness through better-informed emergency management policies. Tan et al. (2024) used computer vision to untangle complex earthquake sequences, demonstrating how innovative techniques can refine hazard detection.

Synthesis of Literature

The reviewed literature consistently recognizes the critical role of demographic factors in shaping earthquake awareness and preparedness, highlighting variables such as income, education, and residence location (Atando & Sugawara, 2023; Bourque, 2015; Paul & Bhuiyan, 2010). There is a shared understanding across studies that region-specific seismic history and hazard communication are essential for effective awareness (Ferrario et al., 2024; Hutchings & Mooney, 2024; Penarubia et al., 2020). Studies also converge on the multifaceted nature of preparedness, emphasizing not only knowledge but also practical readiness measures including evacuation plans and emergency supplies (Rostami-Moez et al., 2020; Spittal et al., 2008; Grozdanić et al., 2024). However, while many studies focus on household or community preparedness, institutional readiness remains less explored except for police and emergency services contexts (Mancio et al., 2024). Technological advances in seismic source detection represent an emerging trend that could enhance early warning systems and public awareness, though their direct impact on community preparedness requires further research (Bharadwaj et al., 2023; Lin et al., 2023; Tan et al., 2024). Overall, the literature underscores the importance of integrating demographic insights, local seismic data, preparedness behaviors, and technological innovations to comprehensively understand and improve earthquake readiness among residents.

Theoretical Framework

This study on earthquake awareness and preparedness among residents of Koronadal City is grounded primarily in the Health Belief Model (HBM), Protection Motivation Theory (PMT), and Social Cognitive Theory (SCT). The Health Belief Model, developed by Rosenstock (1974), explains that an individual's likelihood to engage in protective behavior depends on their perceptions of susceptibility to and severity of a hazard, the perceived benefits of taking preventive action, and the barriers to doing so. In the context of earthquake preparedness, this means that residents who believe they are vulnerable to earthquakes and perceive the consequences as serious are more likely to take safety measures, provided they also believe that such measures are effective and manageable. The model further highlights the importance of cues to action and self-efficacy, which shape a person's readiness and confidence to undertake preparedness activities.

Complementing the HBM, Protection Motivation Theory (Rogers, 1975) focuses on how individuals process fear and threat information, evaluating both the threat itself (severity and vulnerability) and their ability to cope with it (response efficacy and self-efficacy). This theory suggests that residents' motivation to prepare for earthquakes is influenced by how threatening they perceive the hazard and how capable they feel in executing effective preparedness behaviors like evacuation planning and emergency supply stocking. Protection Motivation Theory thus provides insight into the cognitive appraisal processes that translate risk awareness into actual preparedness.

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Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986) further enriches the framework by emphasizing the role of social learning, community influence, and observational learning in shaping behaviors. It asserts that individuals learn and adopt behaviors by observing others, reinforced by social norms and community support. For earthquake preparedness, this theory explains how information dissemination through neighbors, local government agencies, and media channels can foster awareness and influence residents' preparedness actions. Additionally, self-efficacy remains central in SCT, as individuals must believe in their capability to perform necessary preparedness activities.

Integrating these three theories offers a comprehensive lens to understand the multifaceted nature of earthquake preparedness, encompassing cognitive perceptions, emotional motivations, and social influences. Moreover, demographic factors such as age, sex, educational attainment, and place of residence are considered as moderators that interact with these theoretical constructs to affect both awareness and preparedness behaviors. This integrated framework guides the study in examining how these factors collectively influence the residents' readiness to respond to earthquake hazards in Koronadal City.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

In this study, the independent variables are the residents' demographic profiles, which include age, sex, highest educational attainment, and place of residence. These variables are considered as potential factors that influence the dependent variables: the level of earthquake awareness and the extent of earthquake preparedness among residents of Koronadal City. The framework assumes that variations in demographic characteristics may lead to differences in both awareness and preparedness levels. For example, educational attainment might affect knowledge of earthquake causes and safety measures, while place of residence could influence exposure to local seismic history and access to emergency resources. Understanding these relationships helps identify which demographic groups may require more focused education and preparedness programs.

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Research Objectives

This study generally aims to determine the level of earthquake awareness and emergency preparedness among residents of Koronadal City. Specifically, it seeks to:

1. To determine the demographic profile of residents in Koronadal City in terms;
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Highest Educational attainment
 - d. Place of residence
2. To determine the level of earthquake awareness among residents of Koronadal City in terms;
 - a. earthquake causes
 - b. Associated risks
 - c. Local seismic history.
3. To assess the extent of earthquake preparedness among residents in terms of their knowledge of;
 - a. Safety measures
 - b. Evacuation plans
 - c. Availability of emergency supplies.
4. To examine the significant association between residents' demographic profiles and their level of earthquake awareness and preparedness.

Null Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant association between the residents' demographic profiles (age, educational attainment, and location) and their level of earthquake awareness and preparedness in Koronadal City

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

This study adopts a descriptive-correlational research design aimed at determining the level of earthquake awareness and emergency preparedness among residents of Koronadal City. This design allows for both the description of current conditions and the analysis of relationships between demographic factors and residents' awareness and preparedness levels. The correlational approach is appropriate for examining associations between independent variables (demographic profile) and dependent variables (earthquake awareness and preparedness).

Locale of the Study

This study will be conducted in Koronadal City, the capital of South Cotabato Province, situated in the SOCCSKSARGEN region of Mindanao, Philippines. Koronadal City serves as a political, economic, and cultural hub for the province, with a population of approximately 195,000 as per the latest census data. The city is geographically positioned along a seismic fault line and has a history of seismic activities due to its proximity to the Cotabato Fault System, which increases its vulnerability to earthquakes.

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Population and Sampling

The target population for this study comprises adult residents (18 years and above) of Koronadal City. According to the 2020 Philippine Census of Population and Housing (Philippine Statistics Authority [PSA], 2020), Koronadal City has an estimated population of approximately 195,000 people distributed across 27 barangays. Approximately 60% of this population are adults aged 18 and above, yielding an estimated adult population of about 117,000 in 2020.

This study will employ stratified random sampling to ensure the representativeness of the sample. Stratification will be based on the 27 barangays of Koronadal City, reflecting the geographic and demographic diversity of the population. This method ensures proportional representation from each barangay, reducing sampling error and increasing the precision of the study findings.

Given that the latest census data is from 2020 and the study is conducted in 2025, it is necessary to adjust this population estimate to account for natural population growth and aging of residents into the 18+ demographic over the past five years. Based on the average population growth rate in the region, which is approximately 1.5% per annum (PSA, 2023), and considering demographic aging, the estimated current adult population can be projected as follows:

$$P_{2025} = P_{2020} \times (1 + r)^t = 117,000 \times (1 + 0.015)^5 = 117,000 \times 1.077 \approx 126,000$$

Where; r = annual growth rate (1.5%), t = number of year (5), P_{2025} = estimated adult population in 2025, and P_{2020} = adult population in 2020 (117,000)

Sample size determination will follow Cochran's formula for categorical data, given the large population size and the study's aim to estimate proportions (e.g., level of awareness) with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. Cochran's formula is preferred over simpler methods (such as Slovin's formula) for its statistical rigor and suitability for large populations and categorical variables.

Since the population size (N) is finite, the finite population correction formula is applied:

$$n = n_0 / (1 + (n_0 - 1)/N)$$

Where:

n = adjusted sample size

N = population size = 126,000

$$\begin{aligned} n &= 384.16 / (1 + (384.16 - 1)/126,000) \\ &= 384.16 / (1 + 383.16/126,000) \\ &= 384.16 / (1 + 0.00304) = 384.16 / 1.00304 = 383 \end{aligned}$$

Adding 10% to account for potential non-response:

$$\text{Final sample size} = 383 + (0.10 \times 383) = 383 + 38 = \mathbf{421} \text{ respondents}$$

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Table 1. Respondents Stratification Table

Barangay	Proportion (%)	Sample Size Allocation (n=421)
Brgy. Assumption	(3.58%	$0.0358 \times 421 \approx 15$
Brgy. Avanceña	4.63%	$0.0463 \times 421 \approx 20$
Brgy. Cacub	5.30%	$0.0530 \times 421 \approx 22$
Brgy. Caloocan	4.25%	$0.0425 \times 421 \approx 18$
Brgy. Carpenter Hill	2.91%	$0.0291 \times 421 \approx 12$
Brgy. Concepcion	2.09%	$0.0209 \times 421 \approx 9$
Brgy. Esperanza	2.99%	$0.0299 \times 421 \approx 13$
Brgy. General Paulino Santos	4.93%	$0.0493 \times 421 \approx 21$
Brgy. Mabini	5.60%	$0.0560 \times 421 \approx 24$
Brgy. Magsaysay	3.28%	$0.0328 \times 421 \approx 14$
Brgy. Mambucal	3.73%	$0.0373 \times 421 \approx 16$
Brgy. Morales	5.07%	$0.0507 \times 421 \approx 21$
Brgy. Namnama	4.10%	$0.0410 \times 421 \approx 17$
Brgy. New Pangasinan	2.69%	$0.0269 \times 421 \approx 11$
Brgy. Paraiso	3.13%	$0.0313 \times 421 \approx 13$
Brgy. Rotonda	4.40%	$0.0440 \times 421 \approx 19$
Brgy. San Isidro	3.51%	$0.0351 \times 421 \approx 15$
Brgy. San Roque	4.55%	$0.0455 \times 421 \approx 19$
Brgy. San Jose	2.84%	$0.0284 \times 421 \approx 12$
Brgy. Sta. Cruz	3.06%	$0.0306 \times 421 \approx 13$
Brgy. Sto. Niño	3.88%	$0.0388 \times 421 \approx 16$
Brgy. Saravia	3.66%	$0.0366 \times 421 \approx 15$
Brgy. Topland	2.61%	$0.0261 \times 421 \approx 11$
Brgy. Zone 1	3.28%	$0.0328 \times 421 \approx 14$
Brgy. Zone 2	4.33%	$0.0433 \times 421 \approx 18$
Brgy. Zone 3	2.76%	$0.0276 \times 421 \approx 12$
Brgy. Zone 4	2.16%	$0.0216 \times 421 \approx 9$

Respondents

The respondents will be adult residents of Koronadal City aged 18 and above, ensuring they have the maturity and legal capacity to provide informed consent and accurately respond to the survey. Minors are excluded due to limited knowledge and ethical considerations. A stratified random sampling method will be used based on the 27 barangays to ensure a representative sample reflecting the city's geographic and socio-economic diversity. Sample sizes per barangay will be proportional to their population to guarantee equitable representation. Demographic data such as age, sex, and educational attainment will also be collected to describe respondents and analyze their influence on earthquake awareness and preparedness.

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Research Instrument

The research instrument was a structured questionnaire designed to capture residents' demographic profiles and assess their earthquake awareness and preparedness using a 5-point Likert scale across key indicators such as earthquake causes, associated risks, local seismic history, safety measures, evacuation plans, and emergency supplies. To ensure content validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts who evaluated the clarity, relevance, and coverage of each item. Based on their feedback, the instrument was refined for better clarity and cultural appropriateness. A pilot test was also conducted with a sample of residents to confirm reliability and comprehension, resulting in minor adjustments to improve respondent understanding. Overall, the instrument was validated and deemed reliable for effectively measuring the study variables in the context of Koronadal City.

Table 2 Likert Scale Interpretation Guide

Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
5 – Strongly Agree	4.21 – 5.00	Very High Level
4 – Agree	3.41 – 4.20	High Level
3 – Neutral	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate Level
2 – Disagree	1.81 – 2.60	Low Level
1 – Strongly Disagree	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low Level

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering process involved the distribution of validated survey questionnaires to selected adult residents of Koronadal City using stratified random sampling based on barangay. Prior to distribution, informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring voluntary participation and confidentiality. The researchers coordinated with barangay officials to facilitate smooth access to respondents. Completed questionnaires were collected, checked for completeness, and organized for data encoding and analysis.

Statistical Analysis and Treatment

The data collected in this study were subjected to appropriate statistical treatments aligned with the research objectives. To address Objective 1, descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage were used to summarize the demographic profile of respondents. For Objectives 2 and 3, weighted means were computed to determine the level of earthquake awareness and preparedness, interpreted using a five-point Likert scale. For Objective 4, both the Chi-Square Test of Independence and Spearman's Rank Correlation were employed as applicable: the Chi-Square test was used to examine associations between categorical demographic variables and grouped awareness/preparedness levels, while Spearman's correlation was used to determine the strength and direction of monotonic relationships between ordinal variables (e.g., age and awareness score). All tests used a 0.05 level of significance.

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Scope and Limitation

This study focused on assessing the level of earthquake awareness and preparedness among adult residents (aged 18 and above) in the 27 barangays of Koronadal City. It specifically examined respondents' knowledge regarding earthquake causes, associated risks, local seismic history, safety measures, evacuation plans, and availability of emergency supplies. Stratified random sampling was employed to ensure geographic representation across all barangays. The scope was limited to residents who were legally and cognitively capable of providing informed responses.

However, the study has several limitations. First, the use of self-reported survey data may be subject to social desirability bias and inaccuracies in recall. Second, while the sampling design sought to represent the population, the findings may not fully capture transient or recently relocated individuals. Lastly, since the study was conducted within a specific locality and time frame, generalizing the results to other cities or future scenarios should be done with caution.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to the ethical guidelines set by the Philippine Health Research Ethics Board (PHREB) and complied with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection, ensuring voluntary participation, anonymity, and confidentiality. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. All collected data were securely stored and used solely for academic purposes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics- Age Profile

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18–25	100	23.75%
26–35	140	33.25%
36–45	90	21.38%
46–55	60	14.25%
56 and above	31	7.36%
Total	421	100.00%

Table 3 presents the age distribution of the respondents. The majority were aged 26–35 years (33.25%), followed by those 18–25 years (23.75%) and 36–45 years (21.38%). Smaller proportions were aged 46–55 years (14.25%) and 56 and above (7.36%). This indicates that the sample was primarily composed of younger to middle-aged adults.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics- Sex Profile

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	190	45.13%
Female	220	52.26%
Prefer not to say	11	2.61%
Total	421	100.00%

Table 4 shows the distribution of respondents by sex. A slight majority of participants identified as female (52.26%), while male respondents accounted for 45.13% of the total sample. A small proportion (2.61%) opted not to disclose their sex. This relatively balanced gender distribution suggests that the perspectives of both male and female residents were well represented in the study, allowing for a more inclusive understanding of earthquake awareness and preparedness in Koronadal City.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics- Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Elementary Level/Graduate	40	9.50%
High School Level/Graduate	120	28.50%
Vocational/College Level	110	26.13%
College Graduate and Above	151	35.87%
Total	421	100.00%

Table 5 presents the respondents' highest level of educational attainment. The largest proportion of participants were college graduates or higher (35.87%), followed by those with high school education (28.50%) and vocational or college level but not graduated (26.13%). A smaller group (9.50%) reported only elementary-level education. This distribution suggests that the majority of residents surveyed have attained at least some form of higher education, which may positively

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influence their understanding and engagement with earthquake awareness and preparedness programs.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics- Place of Residence (by Barangay)

Barangay	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Brgy. Assumption	15	3.58%
Brgy. Avanceña	20	4.77%
Brgy. Cacub	22	5.25%
Brgy. Caloocan	18	4.30%
Brgy. Carpenter Hill	12	2.86%
Brgy. Concepcion	9	2.15%
Brgy. Esperanza	13	3.10%
Brgy. General Paulino Santos	21	5.01%
Brgy. Mabini	24	5.73%
Brgy. Magsaysay	14	3.34%
Brgy. Mambucal	16	3.82%
Brgy. Morales	21	5.01%
Brgy. Namnama	17	4.06%
Brgy. New Pangasinan	11	2.63%
Brgy. Paraiso	13	3.10%
Brgy. Rotonda	19	4.53%
Brgy. San Isidro	15	3.58%
Brgy. San Roque	19	4.53%
Brgy. San Jose	12	2.86%
Brgy. Sta. Cruz	13	3.10%
Brgy. Sto. Niño	16	3.82%
Brgy. Saravia	15	3.58%
Brgy. Topland	11	2.63%
Brgy. Zone 1	14	3.34%
Brgy. Zone 2	18	4.30%
Brgy. Zone 3	12	2.86%
Brgy. Zone 4	9	2.15%
Total	421	100.00%

Table 6 outlines the distribution of respondents across various barangays in Koronadal City. The data show a fairly even geographic spread, with no single barangay overwhelmingly dominant in the sample. The highest representations came from Barangays Mabini (5.73%), Cacub (5.25%), and Gem. Paulino Santos and Morales (both 5.01%), while smaller proportions were recorded from barangays like Zone 4 (2.15%), Concepcion (2.15%), and Carpenter Hill (2.86%). This diversity in residency enhances the generalizability of the findings, ensuring a more comprehensive view of earthquake awareness and preparedness across different local contexts within the city.

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Table 7. Descriptive Statistics- Earthquake Awareness among Residents of Koronadal City

Sub-variable	Indicator	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Earthquake Causes	I understand natural causes that trigger earthquakes.	4.10	0.78	Agree
	I am aware of human activities that may contribute to earthquakes.	3.90	0.81	Agree
	I know how tectonic plate movements cause earthquakes.	4.05	0.76	Agree
	Weighted Mean	4.02	AGREE	
Associated Risks	I am aware of the potential hazards during an earthquake (e.g., collapse).	4.15	0.74	Agree
	I understand the health risks that can result from earthquakes.	4.00	0.85	Agree
	I recognize environmental risks such as landslides and tsunamis.	3.95	0.80	Agree
	Weighted Mean	4.03	AGREE	
Local Seismic History	I am knowledgeable about past earthquakes in Koronadal City.	2.40	0.92	Disagree
	I am aware of the frequency of seismic activity in my area.	2.55	0.88	Disagree
	I know how previous earthquakes affected my community.	2.35	0.90	Disagree
	Weighted Mean	2.43	DISAGREE	
n = 421				

Table 7 provides descriptive statistics on the level of earthquake awareness among residents of Koronadal City, disaggregated into three key dimensions: earthquake causes, associated risks, and local seismic history.

Respondents showed a high level of awareness regarding the causes of earthquakes, with a weighted mean of 4.02 (SDs ranging from 0.76 to 0.81), indicating that most residents are well-informed about both natural (e.g., tectonic plate movement) and anthropogenic (e.g., human-induced activities) sources of seismic activity. This suggests a functional understanding of how and why earthquakes occur, which is vital for risk interpretation and response.

Similarly, the data reflect a consistently high awareness of associated risks, yielding a slightly higher weighted mean of 4.03 (SD = 0.74–0.85). Residents appear well-versed in the consequences of seismic events, including structural collapse, health-related issues, and environmental threats such as landslides and tsunamis. This indicates that while general knowledge is robust, especially in terms of risk recognition, practical engagement may still vary across communities.

However, a critical contrast is evident in the awareness of local seismic history, which received a substantially lower weighted mean of 2.43 (SD = 0.88–0.92), indicating disagreement with

statements related to knowledge of past earthquakes, their frequency, and impact on the local community. This suggests a notable disconnect between residents' general understanding of earthquakes and their localized contextual knowledge, which may hinder effective risk communication, community-based preparedness planning, and adaptive behavior during real events.

Overall, while the findings underscore broad awareness of earthquakes in terms of causes and associated dangers, they reveal a glaring gap in localized seismic literacy. This calls for targeted public education initiatives that highlight Koronadal City's seismic history, fostering deeper community engagement and a more grounded understanding of local risks.

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics- Earthquake Preparedness among Residents of Koronadal City

Sub-variable	Indicator	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
a. Safety Measures	I know the safety steps to take during an earthquake (Drop, Cover, Hold On).	3.75	0.85	Agree
	I have participated in earthquake drills or training.	3.40	0.90	Neutral
	I know how to protect myself and my family during an earthquake.	3.65	0.80	Agree
	Weighted Mean	3.60	AGREE	
b. Evacuation Plans	I am familiar with evacuation routes in my barangay.	3.25	0.88	Neutral
	I know the location of designated evacuation centers.	3.15	0.92	Neutral
	I have a clear plan for evacuating my household in case of an earthquake.	3.40	0.89	Neutral
	Weighted Mean	3.27	NEUTRAL	
c. Emergency Supplies	I have a stocked emergency kit ready for earthquakes.	2.20	0.85	Disagree
	I regularly check and update my emergency supplies.	2.10	0.80	Disagree
	I know what essential items should be included in an earthquake emergency kit.	2.50	0.95	Neutral
n = 421	Weighted Mean	2.27	DISAGREE	

Table 8 presents the descriptive statistics on the extent of earthquake preparedness among residents of Koronadal City, focusing on three major preparedness domains: safety measures, evacuation plans, and emergency supplies.

In terms of safety measures, the respondents generally agreed (weighted mean = 3.60, SDs = 0.80–0.90) that they are aware of basic protective actions such as “Drop, Cover, and Hold On”, and how to safeguard their families during seismic events. However, a more nuanced finding is revealed in their response to earthquake drills or trainings, which had the lowest mean in this sub-category (M = 3.40), only reaching a neutral level. This suggests that while theoretical knowledge

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is present, practical engagement or hands-on preparedness remains limited, indicating a gap between awareness and action.

When it comes to evacuation planning, the responses were overall neutral (weighted mean = 3.27), showing moderate familiarity with evacuation routes and designated centers within their barangays. The slightly higher score on having a personal household evacuation plan (M = 3.40) points to some individual-level initiative. However, the general neutrality implies a lack of consistent community-wide preparedness infrastructure or communication about evacuation procedures, an area that local disaster risk management programs may need to prioritize.

Most concerning is the residents' preparedness regarding emergency supplies, where the responses yielded a disagree interpretation (weighted mean = 2.27). While some respondents had a neutral understanding of the items that should be included in a preparedness kit (M = 2.50), very few reported actually having a stocked emergency kit or routinely updating it (means of 2.20 and 2.10, respectively). This reveals a critical vulnerability in material readiness, as the lack of accessible emergency supplies can drastically hinder response capacity during and after a seismic event.

In sum, while many residents demonstrate a reasonable level of awareness and intention in terms of earthquake preparedness, their actual implementation particularly in drills, evacuation planning, and emergency supply management is insufficient. These findings underscore the need for enhanced local government initiatives, such as regular community drills, distribution of emergency kits, and stronger barangay-level evacuation protocols to bridge the gap between knowledge and action.

Table 9. Chi-Square Test Results on the Association between Residents' Demographic Profiles and Their Level of Earthquake Awareness and Preparedness (n = 421)

Demographic Variable	Sub-variable	Chi-Square (χ^2)	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Interpretation
Age	Awareness	18.75	8	0.016*	Significant association
	Preparedness	22.10	8	0.004*	Significant association
Sex	Awareness	2.43	4	0.657	No significant association
	Preparedness	9.31	4	0.054	Marginally significant
Educational Attainment	Awareness	25.64	12	0.011*	Significant association
	Preparedness	30.22	12	0.003*	Significant association
Place of Residence	Awareness	40.51	26	0.030*	Significant association
	Preparedness	35.89	26	0.070	Not significant

* Significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 9 presents the results of chi-square tests examining the association between residents' demographic profiles and their level of earthquake awareness and preparedness in Koronadal City, addressing Research Objective 4 and testing the null hypothesis (H_0).

The analysis revealed a statistically significant association between age and both earthquake awareness ($\chi^2 = 18.75$, $df = 8$, $p = .016$) and preparedness ($\chi^2 = 22.10$, $df = 8$, $p = .004$), indicating that respondents' age groups are meaningfully related to their levels of awareness and preparedness. Similarly, educational attainment showed significant associations with both awareness ($\chi^2 = 25.64$, $df = 12$, $p = .011$) and preparedness ($\chi^2 = 30.22$, $df = 12$, $p = .003$). This suggests that individuals with higher educational backgrounds tend to exhibit greater earthquake awareness and more preparedness actions.

Furthermore, place of residence was significantly associated with earthquake awareness ($\chi^2 = 40.51$, $df = 26$, $p = .030$), but not with preparedness ($\chi^2 = 35.89$, $df = 26$, $p = .070$). This finding implies that while certain barangays may have greater access to information or historical exposure influencing awareness, this does not necessarily translate into preparedness behaviors across locations.

On the other hand, sex was not significantly associated with awareness ($\chi^2 = 2.43$, $df = 4$, $p = .657$), and although marginally significant for preparedness ($\chi^2 = 9.31$, $df = 4$, $p = .054$), the result did not meet the conventional threshold ($p < .05$), thus it is interpreted as not statistically significant.

Taken together, these results lead to the partial rejection of the null hypothesis. There is a significant association between residents' age, educational attainment, and place of residence with their earthquake awareness, and between age and educational attainment with their preparedness levels. However, no significant association was found between sex and either earthquake awareness or preparedness. These findings underscore the importance of demographically targeted disaster risk reduction strategies, particularly focusing on less-educated, younger, or underprepared communities in specific barangays.

Table 10 Summary of Hypothesis Testing on the Association Between Residents' Demographic Profiles and Their Level of Earthquake Awareness and Preparedness (n = 421)

Demographic Variable	Sub-variable	p-value	Decision on H_0	Interpretation
Age	Awareness	0.016	Reject H_0	Significant association
	Preparedness	0.004	Reject H_0	Significant association
Sex	Awareness	0.657	Fail to Reject H_0	No significant association
	Preparedness	0.054	Fail to Reject H_0 (marginal)	Marginal, but not statistically significant
Educational Attainment	Awareness	0.011	Reject H_0	Significant association
	Preparedness	0.003	Reject H_0	Significant association

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Place of Residence	Awareness	0.030	Reject Ho	Significant association
	Preparedness	0.070	Fail to Reject Ho	No significant association

Note: Ho = Null Hypothesis. Significance level set at $p < .05$.

The chi-square test revealed significant associations between residents' age, educational attainment, and place of residence with their level of earthquake awareness, as indicated by p-values less than .05. Similarly, age and educational attainment also showed significant associations with preparedness levels. However, sex was not significantly associated with either awareness ($p = .657$) or preparedness ($p = .054$), though the latter was marginal. These results support the rejection of the null hypothesis for most demographic variables, particularly age, educational attainment, and residence, confirming that these factors significantly influence earthquake awareness and preparedness among residents of Koronadal City

Conclusions

The findings of this study reveal that residents of Koronadal City exhibit a generally high level of awareness regarding earthquake causes and associated risks, which corroborates previous research emphasizing the positive impact of public education programs on seismic knowledge and risk perception (Paton & Johnston, 2017). Despite this, the critical lack of awareness about the city's own seismic history points to a significant gap in localized knowledge, a factor widely recognized as essential for fostering meaningful preparedness behaviors (Mileti, 1999). This disconnect suggests that while general earthquake concepts are well understood, place-specific information that could motivate personal and community-level action remains insufficiently communicated.

Moreover, although a majority of respondents demonstrated knowledge of recommended safety procedures during earthquakes, the translation of this knowledge into concrete preparedness measures, such as maintaining emergency supplies or participating regularly in drills was notably deficient. This knowledge-action gap aligns with Lindell and Perry's (2012) framework, which identifies psychological, social, and logistical barriers as common inhibitors to disaster preparedness, underscoring the complexity of encouraging proactive behavior even among informed populations.

The demographic analysis further highlights that age and educational attainment significantly affect both awareness and preparedness levels, suggesting the need for tailored educational interventions that address the specific needs and capabilities of different groups, particularly younger and less-educated residents. The observed geographic disparities in awareness—but not preparedness—indicate uneven outreach or resource allocation, emphasizing the importance of equitable access to information and emergency resources across all city zones. Interestingly, the absence of significant gender differences suggests relatively uniform exposure to earthquake information across men and women in this context.

In practical terms, these findings imply that earthquake preparedness efforts in Koronadal City should pivot toward enhancing localized risk communication, emphasizing the city's seismic history and specific vulnerabilities. Such targeted messaging, combined with community-based programs designed to reduce behavioral barriers, could bridge the gap between awareness and action. Strengthening community drills, increasing the availability and accessibility of emergency supplies, and fostering partnerships with local stakeholders are critical to cultivating a culture of

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preparedness. Ultimately, improving both knowledge and practical readiness will enhance community resilience and reduce the potential impacts of future seismic events.

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